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Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
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МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Akhmedova D.I., Ruzmatova D.M. CLINICAL EXAMPLES OF CARDIOMYOPATHY IN CHILDREN.....	6
2. Akhmedova D.I., Mamatkulova R.I. JUVENILE RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS WITH AN EARLY ONSET: A CASE REPORT.....	11
3. Kayumova Nilufar Nigmatjanovna A MODERN VIEW OF THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF INFLAMMATORY COMPLICATIONS IN ACUTE PURULENT ODONTOGENIC OSTITIS IN CHILDREN (LITERATURE REVIEW).....	16
4. M.N. Tillyashaikhov, S.V. Kamishov, K.Sh. Izrailbekova THE FREQUENCY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MULTIPLE PRIMARY MALIGNANT TUMORS OF THE FEMALE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM.....	22
5. Kayumova Nilufar Nigmatjanovna COMPARATIVE DYNAMICS OF IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF ORAL FLUID IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE PURULENT ODONTOGENIC OSTITIS OF THE JAW IN THE TREATMENT OF STANDARD AND COMPLEX THERAPY WITH THE USE OF ENZYME THERAPY.....	29
6. Kamilov Kh.P., Takhirova K.A., Ibragimov O.D., Komilova A.Z. MICROBIOLOGICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL FEATURES OF MULTIFORM EXUDATIVE ERYTHEMA OF THE MOUTH.....	34
7. Ulugmuratov A.A., Khidirov L.A. EXPRESSION OF MICRORNA LEVELS IN INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION IN CHILDREN.....	42
8. Mamarizaev I.K., Abdukadirova Sh.B., Djuraev Dj.D. THE ROLE OF THE HEMOSTATIC SYSTEM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACUTE OBSTRUCTIVE BRONCHITIS IN CHILDREN AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF MYOCARDITIS.....	47
9. Alyavi A.L., Latipov A.Ya., Pulatova Sh.H. ROLE OF SODIUM URETIC PEPTIDES IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF HEART FAILURE IN POST-INFRACT CARDIOSCLEROSIS.....	52
10. Kamilov X.P., Kadirbayeva A.A., Ibodullayeva Sh.A. ETIOPATHOGENETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CHRONIC CATARRHAL GINGIVITIS.....	56

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Kamilov Xaydar PozilovichProfessor, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
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Associate Professor of the Department of Therapeutic Dentistry

Ibodullayeva Shaxnoza AlisherovnaMaster of the 1st year of study, Department of Therapeutic Dentistry

Tashkent State Dental Institute

Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent.

Ibodullaevasahnoza65@gmail.com.

ETIOPATHOGENETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CHRONIC CATARRHAL GINGIVITIS <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10147113>**ABSTRACT**

Oral mucous diseases are one of dentistry's most complex, urgent problems. To date, they have been least studied in terms of etiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis and especially treatment, among other dental diseases. Currently, there are relatively accurate clinical criteria for diagnosing inflammatory periodontal diseases. There are many different methods of treating gingivitis, which reflect the attempts of researchers and clinicians to have a therapeutic effect on various links in the pathogenesis of the pathological process. However, despite the significant achievements of modern dentistry, the frequency of relapses of transition to the developed forms of inflammatory diseases remains high. Progressive lesions of the periapical tissues often lead to the loss of teeth and can be a source of many diseases. Therefore, the urgency of the problem of detection, diagnosis, and treatment of gingivitis comes to the fore and requires careful study and search for ways and effective methods of providing dental care.

Keywords: catarrhal gingivitis, oral mucosa, microbial flora, periodontal disease, relapse.

Камилов Хайдар Позиловичпрофессор, д.м.н., заведующий кафедрой
Госпитальная терапевтическая стоматология**Кадырбаева Алиа Арстановна**

PhD, доцент кафедры госпитальной терапевтической стоматологии

Ибодуллаева Шахноза Алишеровна

Магистр 1го года обучения, кафедра Госпитальная терапевтическая стоматология

Ташкентский государственный стоматологический институт

Республика Узбекистан, г.Ташкент.

Ibodullaevasahnoza65@gmail.com

ЭТИОПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО КАТАРАЛЬНОГО ГИНГИВИТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Заболевания слизистой оболочки полости рта являются одной из наиболее сложных, актуальных проблем стоматологии, и до настоящего времени они наименее изучены с точки зрения этиологии, патогенеза, диагностики и особенно лечения среди других стоматологических заболеваний. На сегодняшний момент существуют достаточно точные клинические критерии диагностики воспалительных заболеваний - пародонта, имеется большое количество различных методов лечения гингивита, которые отражают попытки исследователей и клиницистов оказывать лечебное воздействие на различные звенья патогенеза патологического процесса. Однако несмотря на значительные достижения современной стоматологии, остается высокой частота рецидивов перехода в развившиеся формы воспалительных заболеваний. Прогрессирующее поражение околоверхнечерных тканей нередко приводит к утрате зубов и может явиться источником многих заболеваний. Поэтому актуальность проблемы выявления, диагностики, лечения гингивита выступает на первый план и требует внимательного изучения и поиска путей и эффективных методов оказания стоматологической помощи.

Ключевые слова: катаральный гингивит, слизистая оболочка полости рта, микробная флора, пародонт, рецидив.

Камилов Хайдар Позилович

профессор, т.ф.д., Госпитал терапевтик стоматология кафедраси мудир

Кадырбаева Алия Арстановна

PhD, Госпитал терапевтик стоматология кафедраси доценти

Ибодуллаева Шахноза Алишеровна

Госпитал терапевтик стоматология кафедраси 1 курс магистр талабаси

Тошкент Давлат стоматология институти

Ўзбекистон Республикаси, Тошкент ш.

Ibodullaevasahnoza65@gmail.com

СУРУНКАЛИ КАТАРАЛ ГИНГИВИТНИНГ ЭТИОПАТОГЕНЕТИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Оғиз бушлик шиллик пардаси касалликлари стоматологиянинг энг мураккаб, долзарб муаммоларидан бири бўлиб, ҳозиргача улар бошқа тиш касалликлари орасида этиология, патогенез, диагностика ва айниқса даволаш бўйича энг кам ўрганилган. Ҳозирги вақтда яллиғланишли периодонтал касалликларни ташхислаш учун жуда аниқ клиник мезонлар мавжуд. Гингивитни даволаш учун жуда кўп турли хил усуллар мавжуд бўлиб, улар тадқиқотчилар ва клинисенларнинг патологик жараён патогенезининг турли қисмларига терапевтик таъсир кўрсатишга уринишларини акс эттиради. Бироқ, замонавий стоматологиянинг муҳим ютуқларига қарамай, яллиғланиш касалликларининг ривожланган шаклларига ўтишнинг қайталаниш тезлиги юқори бўлиб қолмоқда. Периапикал тўқималарнинг прогрессив шикастланиши кўпинча тишларнинг йўқолишига олиб келади ва кўплаб касалликларнинг манбаи бўлиши мумкин.

Калит сўзлар: катарал гингивит, оғиз бўшлиғи шиллик қавати, микроб флораси, ferment, пародонт.

Relevant. Periodontal tissue diseases are one of the most significant problems in modern dentistry, as there is an increase in the incidence of young people. There is a connection between individual oral hygiene, the amount of plaque and tartar, and the condition of periodontal tissues. Also, chronic diseases of the internal organs and systems of the human body, including gastrointestinal tract diseases, cardiovascular system and diabetes mellitus, negatively affect

periodontal tissues. It is also known that the prevalence of periodontal tissue diseases is high among patients whose professional activity is directly related to producing non-ferrous and rare metals, powders from them and abrasives. Recently, domestic and foreign researchers have played a great role in the etiology and pathogenesis of periodontal tissue diseases for local causes.

Gingivitis is a pathology directly related to the imbalance between bacterial symbiosis and oral tissues. Analyzing the data from foreign and domestic sources, it can be assumed that three groups of factors play an important role in the etiology of periodontal diseases:

- 1) factors that determine the condition of dental plaque and plaque;
- 2) factors of the oral cavity affecting the pathogenetic potential of microorganisms and their waste products;
- 3) general factors that regulate the metabolism in the tissues of the oral cavity.

Based on a review of the data of the studied literature, it is noted that researchers distinguish non-mineralized and mineralized dental plaque. The mineral components in the oral fluid (calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, carbonates and trace elements) affect the formation of hard dental plaque, the surface of which is in contact with the oral fluid and is covered with a plaque that contains bacteria and microorganisms. Experimental and clinical observations conducted by scientists allowed us to state that the cause of inflammatory processes in the oral cavity is microorganisms (aerobes and anaerobes). The number of aerobic microorganisms in the oral cavity ranges from 91.7% to 94.8%. In chronic catarrhal gingivitis, the most common microorganisms are *St. albus*, *St. aureus*, *Candida albicans*, and anaerobes; most are *E. coli* -*Escherichia coli*. By consuming oxygen from tissues, aerobic microorganisms form substances with high-reducing properties, stimulating bacteroid growth.

Researchers assign an important role in the pathogenesis of the infectious process in the oral cavity to the symbiosis of aerobic microorganisms, both among themselves and aerobes with anaerobic microorganisms. There is evidence from experimental and clinical studies that the mechanism of such symbiosis is based on four components. These are:

1. The disappearance of free oxygen, which is absorbed by aerobic microorganisms;
2. isolation of catalase and superoxidismutase by aerobic microorganisms, which affects the survival of anaerobes;
3. secretion of biologically active substances by aerobic microorganisms that stimulate the growth of anaerobic microorganisms;
4. providing aerobic microorganisms with protection and growth factors that enhance the process of anaerobiosis.

Pathogenicity factors of aerobic and anaerobic microorganisms play an important role in the development of periodontal tissue diseases:

- a) adhesins (factors that are responsible for the attachment of microorganisms to host cells, mainly to epithelial cells);
- b) adaptation factors;
- c) invasins, in other words, penetration factors (substances of a protein nature that allow bacteria to penetrate cells);
- d) aggressins are molecules that have a damaging effect on target cells;
- e) impedines (these are components of microorganisms that cause the weakening of the immune forces of the macroorganism);
- f) modulins (molecules of microorganisms that stimulate the production of cytokines);
- g) capsule of microorganisms (containing a large group of substances with strong antigenic properties);
- h) microbial cytotoxins;
- i) endotoxins (substances that are released by pathogenic microorganisms during their death or destruction of their walls);
- k) exotoxins (substances released by gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria into the environment);
- l) enzymes-toxins or "aggression enzymes";

m) superantigens (substances of protein nature produced by microorganisms capable of causing mass activation of T-lymphocytes);

h) heat shock proteins and many other specific toxic substances of microbial origin.

It is proved that the patient's body's resistance to the pathological process of infectious genesis is due to the peculiarities of his organs and tissues, circulatory system, lymphatic system, and the ability to regenerate properties.

It is known that gram-positive microorganisms are characterized by a mechanism of adhesion or attachment to the protein structure of the patient's body, which leads to the production of extracellular glycocalyx, which creates a barrier against antibiotics and biologically active substances of a specific nature. The coupling of microorganisms with the patient's body's proteins affects the receptors located on the surface of neutrophils, which leads to their activation. Microorganisms such as *St. aureus* and *St. albus* hurt the body because they produce specific enzymes such as hyaluronidase (an enzyme that breaks down hyaluronic acid), coagulase (an enzyme that causes blood clotting) and fibrinolysin (has a fibrinolytic effect), as well as toxins such as leukotoxin (toxin, destroying leukocytes, monocytes, neutrophils) and dermanecrotoxin (a toxin that causes vascular disorders).

Streptococcus also plays an important role in the etiology of chronic catarrhal generalized gingivitis. The pathogenic properties of streptococcus are associated with many traumatic factors, such as streptolysin, hemolysin, fibrinolysin, necrotoxin, and leukocidin. After the polysaccharides of gram-negative microorganisms are combined with the proteins of the patient's body, a lipid-A-bound complex is formed. The lipid-A-linked complex is a mediator of activation of leukocytes and macrophages. Endotoxins increase the release of interleukins, gamma interferon, arachidonic acid degradation products (leukotrienes, thromboxane, prostocyclines), platelet activation factor (FAT), nitric oxide; activate the kallikrein-kinin system, lipid and protein peroxidation; promote the release of neutrophils from bone marrow cells.

Against the background of ischemia, neutrophils move from the blood to endothelial cells. Special macromolecules- selectins, which are localized on the membranes of leukocytes and endothelial cells, thereby serve as an agent for chemotaxis (motor reaction of microorganisms to a chemical stimulus) of neutrophils to the vessel's periphery. With the help of special integrin molecules, neutrophils are firmly fixed to endothelial cells after movement. After that, endothelial cells are reduced, with gaps formed between them. As a result, leukocytes move from the vascular bed into the interstitial (perivascular) space and the gingival fluid. Migrated neutrophils become the fundamental cellular link in the inflammatory reaction of the gingival groove while producing superoxide radical (O_2^-) hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), activating the pentose phosphate and glycolytic pathways of carbohydrate conversion.

Produced by the enzyme myeloperoxidase, the oxygen-dependent mechanism is one of the components of the bactericidal effect of leukocytes. When performing a myeloperoxidase reaction, the concentration of substances with the significant oxidizing ability (OCl-hypochloride, aldehydes, quinones, etc.) is determined. With such a reaction, the lysis of microorganisms neutralization of toxins and inflammatory mediators occurs. If the components of peroxidase catalysis are formed in excess, areas of necrosis appear. In addition to myeloperoxidase, low-molecular non-enzymatic cationic proteins in leukocyte granules (lactoferrin and lysozyme) also have pronounced bactericidal potential.

In the cytolemmas of gram-negative bacteria, a structural transformation occurs due to the action of myeloperoxidase. Because of this, the mechanisms of selective transfer of substances are disrupted, which leads to the suppression of important metabolic processes in bacterial cells, resulting in their death.

All etiological factors that damage periodontal tissues can be divided into primary and secondary: primary is the biofilm of the oral cavity, which causes inflammation, and secondary causes – these include local and general factors that can provoke the primary complex, i.e. microbial flora. Since the late 90s of the last century, the leading role has been assigned to the nonspecific microflora of dental plaque. New bacteroids have been discovered: *Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*, *Prevotella intermedia*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Bacteroides*, etc. The existence of

periodontopathogenic microorganisms has also been proven. In healthy periodontitis, aerobic gram-positive microorganisms predominate and the content of gram-negative bacteria is 10-15% lower, and in periodontitis, this ratio is already reversed (Grudyanov A.I., 2000; Zhazhkov E.N., 2000).

As mentioned above, in periodontal diseases, inflammatory mediators - histamine, serotonin, and bradykinin- are released into the blood, affecting the capillary endothelium and leading to increased vascular permeability. As a result, there is hyperemia, swelling of the gums, soreness, periodontal tissues, and alveolar bone. In the first stages, symptoms of catarrhal gingivitis occur. In the absence of timely treatment, the toxins' effect becomes higher, leading to a shift in pH to the acidic side and the formation of inflammatory mediators (lymphokines, leukotrienes, interleukins, prostaglandin E2). Eventually, under their influence, osteoclasts are activated (bone resorption begins), the dentoalveolar epithelial attachment is destroyed and loosened, and the epithelium germinates in the apical direction, followed by bone lysis (Genco R. J., 2010).

Many studies prove the weakening of the nonspecific and specific immunity of the oral cavity in patients with chronic gingivitis and periodontitis (Bondareva E.S., 2014; Genco R. J., 2010; Berezina. Nako N.V., 2017). Prolonged contact of the microflora of dental deposits, the contents of periodontal pockets with the oral cavity leads to the development of autoimmune processes (Grudyanov A.I., 2000; Dobrodeeva L.K. 2001; Kiselnikova L.P., 2017).

Researchers have been dealing with the etiology, pathogenesis, clinic, treatment and prevention of chronic catarrhal gingivitis for a long time. Enough materials have been collected on this issue. But at the moment, the most important is the timely diagnosis and prevention of gingivitis. To do this, it is necessary to study modern diagnostic measures that can detect gingivitis in the early stages to prevent its complications (Chereshnev V.A., Gusev E.Yu., 2001; Lukinykh L.M., 2005; Utyanskaya E.V., 2006; Kazarina L.N., 2016).

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